

**Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe
Phase 3**

**Service assessment 2
Milestone M4.4**

ESiWACE3 Milestone M4.4

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ESiWACE3 Milestone M4.4

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ESiWACE3 Milestone M4.4

Introduction

For a general introduction into the goals and strategy of the ESiWACE3 Services in work package 4, we refer to the previous Milestone document, submitted in month 18. This assessment reports on the continuation of the work presented in M4.3 and can therefore discuss the first fully completed service projects delivered by ESiWACE3.

To improve clarity and visibility by European Earth system modeling community, we have decided in December 2024 to rename our different service types as follows:

- Service 1 has been renamed to “Services on model optimization, acceleration and HPC exploitation”
- Service 2 has been renamed to “Services on Support on domain specific tools and technologies”

This new terminology has been adopted on the ESiWACE3 website, within promotion material, official call documents and other communication channels. We will continue to use this naming scheme throughout this document for consistency and clarity.

Calls

This report was written in June 2025, Month 30 (M30) of the ESiWACE3 project. So far, we have held 4 calls for proposals for our services on model optimization, acceleration and HPC exploitation. The table below summarizes the submitted and accepted proposals.

Date of Service call closing	Submitted proposals	Accepted proposals
28-06-2023	4 in total	DALES, GLOBO, ESMValTool
01-11-2023	6 in total	OGSTM-BFM, CAMP, MESSy, EC-EARTH4 (to start in July 2024)
03-06-2024	5 in total	WFLOW, TRIXI.jl, NEMO
01-03-2025	7 in total	ICON-0, Delft3D-FM, MESSy2, DALES2

Here we observe that we have slowly been gaining recognition with the ESiWACE3 services, and we were glad to receive 7 proposals in March 2025 after a relatively short period (~1.5 month) of having our call open and being advertised. Unfortunately, 3 of those proposals did not pass our internal review for various reasons, which we discuss below in the evaluation section. Because our staffing capacity matched the number of eligible projects, there was no need to organize a second, external scientific review round.

The ESiWACE3 Service for support on domain specific tools and technologies has recently opened a new call for proposals. After receiving only a single eligible proposal in 2024, we have decided to take the following steps:

- Open the call indefinitely, with a continuing promotion campaign on LinkedIn, the ESiWACE3 newsletter and other channels.

ESiWACE3 Milestone M4.4

- Broaden the scope of the offered tools and technologies to better match the scientific domain and aims of potential collaborators: we added the Automatic Performance Profiling (APP) as a tool for which BSC offers expertise in the climate community, and we added support for easybuild (rather than Spack) to better align with the EuroHPC ecosystem.
- Redirect requests to our services on model optimization, acceleration and HPC exploitation to this stream of services whenever we deem that this is appropriate. One example is the coupled NEMO mixed precision service request, which clearly could be phrased as an application of the AutoRPE tool and therefore suitable as a service on support for tools and technologies.

In the following section we present the results of the finished service projects on model optimization, and an overview of the work done in the ongoing projects.

Services on model optimization, acceleration and HPC exploitation: completed projects

DALES

DALES, the Dutch Atmospheric Large Eddy Simulation, is an MPI-parallel Fortran90 code aimed at the simulation of turbulent boundary layers, convective clouds and fine-scale meteorological phenomena. The code was in transition towards being fully GPU-accelerated using OpenACC when this service project started. The main goal, advancing DALES such that it is capable of running standard test cases involving moist physics and radiative transfers entirely GPU-resident, has been achieved. For this, the following improvements were made:

- Full acceleration of all microphysics schemes available in the model, including simple single-moment bulk schemes as well as schemes involving graupel and snow.
- Upgrade of the radiation library to RTE+RRTMGP, which is capable of executing on GPUs through OpenACC or OpenMP.
- Various fixes and improvements throughout the code to support heterogeneous execution, such as the correctness of restart functionality.

Figure 1: Node-to-node comparison of the GPU-accelerated DALES for the standard RICO test case.

ESiWACE3 Milestone M4.4

The result of our effort for the standard precipitating shallow cumulus test case RICO is presented in Figure 1. This is a comparison on the Dutch national supercomputer Snellius, running the model on a dual-socket 192-core AMD Genoa node against a GPU node with 4 NVidia H100 cards. We observe a satisfying factor ~ 12 speedup whilst maintaining a similar performance profile between the architectures.

GLOBO

GLOBO is an atmospheric general circulation model developed at the Institute of Atmospheric Sciences and Climate of the National Research Council of Italy (CNR-ISAC). GLOBO is currently used as a research tool for predictability studies on different time scales ranging from the short range to the subseasonal scale. It is also used as an operational forecasting tool to provide, on a daily basis, a 7-day global forecast and a 32-day ensemble forecast on a weekly basis.

After profiling using the MAQAO framework (Modular Assembly Quality Analyzer and Optimizer), the following optimisations have been achieved:

- Improve vectorization on AMD processors thanks to AVX2 using the Intel compilers.
- Inline functions called inside some loops.
- Gather communications before waiting for the data to be exchanged.
- Reduce the number of communications by gathering more computations before exchanges.

In total, 9 optimisations have been submitted as separate merge requests. The resulting improved scaling is depicted in Figure 2 for a relatively small test case (KM078) on a 514x362 grid.

Figure 2: Scaling of the GLOBO for the KM078 test case.

ESMValTool

The Earth System Model Evaluation Tool is a community-developed, open-source software framework for the evaluation and analysis of data produced by climate models. For example, it allows comparing output of single or multiple models against results from previous versions or against re-analyses and observations. ESMValTool provides diagnostics for several different realms (e.g., atmosphere, ocean, land, etc.), and is developed with contributions of over 200 developers from more than 60 international institutions.

ESiWACE3 Milestone M4.4

Being a data processing framework rather than an Earth system model, the ESMValTool code faces unique challenges when it comes to performance. The execution speed of processing pipelines is typically limited by storage accesses, and ESMValTool reliance on third-party components makes it hard to track down redundant or sub-optimal access patterns and time-consuming to address them properly. Nevertheless, many redundant data loads were found during metadata calculations throughout the Iris library dependency, and many of them were either fixed with upstream modifications to Iris or circumvented in the ESMValTool core component. The result is a speedup of the vast majority of the preprocessing functions in ESMValTool, as is shown in Figure 3. Furthermore, the scalability of the throughput has improved by ensuring all intermediate data in the processing pipelines are Dask arrays. By eliminating all casting to numpy-arrays, the entire processing graph can be parallelized by Dask and optimally chunked and processed as a data stream. The results for a low-resolution (but long-running and large ensemble) test recipe IPCC-CMIP6 and a high-resolution job HIRES are listed on the right table in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Left: list of all speedups of ESMValCore preprocessor functions after this ESiWACE3 service project. Right: Multi-node scaling of selected processing recipes.

OGSTM-BFM

OGSTM-BFM is a computational model for the advection and interaction of biochemical tracers in oceans. The system consists of two components: the OGS Tracer Model (Lazzari et al., 2010) transport model based on the OPA 8.1 system, and the biogeochemical reactor with the Biogeochemical Flux Model (Vichi et al., 2015, BFM model), managed by the BFM consortium. The model is run operationally at daily frequency to provide relevant information on the marine plankton needed for monitoring biomass productivity, plankton diversity, carbon sequestration and acidification of the Mediterranean Sea marine system.

The original goal of this project was to port the most important subroutines of OGSTM-BFM to GPUs. Within the project, we have defined several OpenACC guidelines to port code on GPU and explained the rationale behind them. We have applied these guidelines to port on GPU the entirety of the OGSTM-BFM application, reducing transfers between CPU and GPU memory to the bare minimum and effectively hiding kernel launch overhead penalties.

We used the Leonardo supercomputer at Cineca as the target platform for benchmarking. The CPU baseline was compiled with Intel Fortran and was executed on a single 'data centric' dual-socket node with 2 Intel Sapphire Rapids 56-core CPUs. The OpenACC version of OGSTM-BFM was compiled using nvhpc and ran on 2 'booster' nodes, each containing 4 NVidia

ESiWACE3 Milestone M4.4

A100 GPU cards. Excluding I/O from this benchmark setup, the accelerated code achieved a **speedup of 7.4** with respect to the baseline.

CAMP

Chemistry Across Multiple Phases (CAMP) is a Fortran library code for a flexible treatment of gas- and aerosol-phase chemical processes in atmospheric models. The library can be integrated into models of diverse scales, from simple box models to global Earth System models. CAMP has an existing GPU implementation for many of its solvers.

The primary goal is to revise and optimize the GPU implementation of the code on Marenostrom 5. The GPU implementation of CAMP includes deep optimization development, which represents a step forward from the current community approach of simply translating the code to GPU, even when the algorithm and data distribution are optimized for a CPU environment, but not as much for the highly parallel GPU architecture.

We upgraded the CAMP solver to run simultaneously on CPU and GPU architectures. We included a new load-balancing algorithm to improve the usage of both architectures compared to manually setting the balance. We conducted a performance analysis of the GPU and CPU versions to identify potential optimizations beyond the scope of the current project.

We have implemented significant improvements to GPU execution, including a 4x reduction in data transfers, which contributes to the acceleration. The load-balancing algorithm adjusts the load for each chemistry time step based on the distribution from the previous time step. The algorithm is designed to stabilize at the optimal load balance, where the CPU and GPU times are nearly equal. The algorithm's code is open source and compressed into fewer than a hundred lines, facilitating future porting to other software. The CPU-GPU version was coupled in MONARCH and tested in a one-day experiment. In a node-against-node comparison, it achieves an **8x speedup** against the CPU version. Additionally, it achieves 58% CPU-GPU usage; in other words, 58% of the execution time, both CPU and GPU resources are utilized simultaneously.

MESSy

The Modular Earth Submodel System model (MESSy), provides a middleware for coupling atmospheric legacy models (e.g., ICON, ECHAM, COSMO) and specialized ESM components, the so-called submodels (e.g., physical parameterizations, chemistry packages, diagnostics) via generalized interfaces. Currently more than 100 submodels are included in MESSy. MESSy is used and further developed by a consortium of 22 European (and further non-European) institutions mostly (but not only) with the focus on chemistry, climate and air quality applications.

The primary objective of this collaboration was to demonstrate a hybrid execution of the chemistry climate model ICON/MESSy, where ICON runs fully on GPUs, while MESSy would primarily operate on CPUs with only a few select submodels executed on GPUs. This setup aimed to evaluate the performance of a middleware expansion designed to minimize data transfer between the base and submodels running on the GPU, thereby enhancing computational efficiency.

The following technical improvements were made to work towards this goal:

ESiWACE3 Milestone M4.4

- The Continuous Integration (CI) pipeline to test the GPU features of the MESSy code, ensuring that any changes could be validated promptly and reliably.
- Porting of the SEDI submodel to enhance its compatibility with the GPU architecture and improve computational efficiency. The SEDI submodel would be then used for ICON/MESSy GPU simulations.
- Focus was shifted toward detaching dependencies from the outdated version of ICON, with an emphasis on allowing MESSy to leverage the latest advancements via the ICON Community Interface (ComIn). This work was crucial to prepare MESSy for future coupling with the latest versions of ICON.
- A concept was designed and implemented for triggering the update of the base model data to the device where the base model is executed on. This was implemented as an expansion of the infrastructure submodel CHANNEL. Unfortunately, testing the functionality of this concept remains to be done.

For benchmarking, the MESSy DWARF has been used. The setup included the full MESSy infrastructure and the submodel SEDI. The employed grid consisted of 10848 horizontal grid boxes and 40 vertical layers. 13 artificial gas (6) and aerosol (7) phase tracers were defined, of which only four aerosol phase tracers were subject to sedimentation. The test case was executed on the Levante supercomputer, specifically focusing on the GPU nodes of the system which have 4 NVidia A100 cards as accelerators. Running this test case on a single node resulted in factor ~ 2 speedup with respect to the AMD-Milan equipped CPU performance (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: Performance of the accelerated SEDI submodel in the MESSy DWARF test case on a single GPU node on the Levante system at DKRZ.

Achieving higher speedup is anticipated and can be measured after the implementation of increased parallelism in the working GPU configuration of ICON/MESSy setup.

Services on model optimization, acceleration and HPC exploitation: ongoing projects

Trixi.jl

Trixi.jl is a numerical simulation framework for conservation laws, written in Julia. In the context of this service we are working together with the Trixi team to improve the performance of their GPU implementation, which is currently based on Julia's KernelAbstractions.jl framework. Acceleration of some functions has already been achieved, and the code is being tested on JEDI

ESiWACE3 Milestone M4.4

(the Jupiter precursor) and Jewels Booster for single node performance and multi-node scalability.

Wflow

Wflow is a hydrological modeling framework written in Julia. In this service we are working to improve the performance of the hydrological simulations by adding support for GPU computations using the KernelAbstractions.jl framework. The bottleneck of the simulations (river flow routing) has seen a significant performance gain on GPU in an isolated case. The modifications to the routine are currently being integrated into the full model.

NEMO

The Nemo ocean engine is a primitive equation model adapted to regional and global ocean circulation problems. This model is written in Fortran and utilizes MPI to distribute the workload across multiple computing nodes. In this new version of the model, the developers have introduced a feature called tiling, which allows for subdividing the domain of each MPI task.

The scope of this project is to implement a hybrid MPI+OpenMP version of the model. The implementation must keep the readability of the source code and take advantage of the new tiling feature introduced in NEMO 5.

The project finished all the setup stages for using the Marenostrum5 supercomputer and the BSC profiling tools with the NEMO5. Also, we started some mock-ups and some preliminary implementations as a proof of concept, but there are no results for the moment.

In addition, we tested some ideas extracted from papers, for improving the performance while implementing the OpenMP+MPI version of NEMO5.

EC-EARTH4-M7

EC-Earth is a state-of-the-art Earth System Model used for climate research, with ongoing efforts to incorporate the M7 aerosol module for improved representation of atmospheric composition. In this service, we are using AutoRPE to optimize the numerical precision of the M7 module. This approach is expected to provide performance gains while maintaining the quality of simulation results, supporting more efficient and accurate climate modeling within EC-Earth.

In this project, we set up the work in a containerized environment to enhance portability and reproducibility. We configured the compilation process and prepared all necessary input files to enable testing with the original code. Once we verified successful runs of the unmodified code, we began applying AutoRPE. This required adapting AutoRPE to support OpenIFS/M7-specific code patterns and modern Fortran syntax. With these adaptations, we were able to process the code and implement the precision emulator. The current step is to update the build system to incorporate the modified source files.

Services on Support on domain specific tools and technologies

RTE+RRTMGP-C++

ESiWACE3 Milestone M4.4

Recently, we have started a project on the application of Kernel Tuner to the RTE+RRTMGP-C++ library. This is a C++ port of the well-known RTE+RRTMGP code that calculates radiative fluxes due to solar and infrared radiative forcing on atmospheric vertical columns. The C++ code contains a native CUDA backend that can already be tuned with the Kernel Tuner tool and the objective of this project is to explore the introduction of mixed precision in this software pipeline. We are focussing our efforts on the expensive calculation of the radiative transport properties of the gas mixture (RTE).

Evaluation

This section evaluates the overall performance of the ESiWACE3 services. Since the last report (Milestone M4.3), the services focused on model optimization, acceleration, and HPC exploitation have been operating smoothly, with no major issues reported. Previous challenges related to staffing have been successfully resolved. Additionally, communication around this service has improved, as evidenced by a slight increase in the number of proposals received in the most recent call. However, the majority of these still originate from the direct network of ESiWACE3 partners.

Conversely, as mentioned in the previous milestone, the number of proposals received for the service on support for domain-specific tools and technologies has remained low. This is largely due to the highly specialized nature of the service, which focuses on specific tools. To address this, several strategies have been implemented to increase proposal submissions:

- Renaming the service to a more accessible and relevant title.
- Launching a new call, which will remain open on a rolling basis until June 2026 or until the allocated budget is exhausted.
- Developing new promotional materials and improving communication efforts.
- Updating the ESiWACE3 website, with particular attention to the Services section.
- Expanding support to include additional tools not originally covered in the DoA, such as Automatic Performance Profiling (developed under WP2) and EasyBuild.

It is worth mentioning that this new call has already received one proposal, which is a resubmission from the other service, and we expect more proposals to come.

Conclusion

In summary, since the launch of ESiWACE3 in January 2023, over a period of 30 months, we have organized four calls for the service on model optimization, acceleration, and HPC exploitation, as well as two calls for the service supporting domain-specific tools and technologies—the second of which is a rolling call currently ongoing. The services have consistently operated effectively, particularly in the area of model optimization and HPC acceleration. Although attracting proposals for the more specialized domain-specific tools and technologies service remains a challenge, the implementation of targeted strategies is expected to significantly expand its visibility and impact.

Importantly, several projects supported through the service on model optimization, acceleration, and HPC exploitation have already been successfully completed, delivering excellent results and clearly demonstrating the value of the support provided—particularly through the collaboration between RSEs and the weather and climate modeling communities. In addition, a number of other projects are currently underway, highlighting the continued relevance and growing demand for the services offered by ESiWACE3.